

SYNTHESIS OF 5-KETO-9-METHOXY-1:2:3:4:4a:5:6:6a:11a:11b-DECA-HYDROCHRYSOFLUORENE

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The condensation of 1-acetyl- $\Delta^{1:2}$ -cyclohexene with 5-methoxy-1-indanone in presence of potassium *tert.*-butoxide furnished 5-keto-9-methoxy-1:2:3:4:4a:5:6:6a:11a:11b-octahydrochrysofluorene which was catalytically reduced to 5-keto-9-methoxy-1:2:3:4:4a:5:6:6a:11a:11b-decahydrochrysofluorene. This compound was oxidised to the lactone (V) which on hydrolysis yielded the hydroxy-acid (VI). The hydroxy-acid was transformed back to the lactone (V).

The presence of perhydrochrysofluorene nucleus in Jervine and its related alkaloids has been definitely established by a series of degradative experiments by Wintersteiner and co-workers (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1951, 73, 2970; 1952, 74, 3842, 4474; 1953, 75, 4938) and Fried and Klingsberg (*ibid.*, 1953, 75, 4929). The selenium dehydrogenation of Jervine also yielded hydrocarbons which were considered to be the homologues of chrysofluorene (Jacobs, Craig and Lavin, *J. Biol. Chem.*, 1941, 131, 51).

With a view to synthesising the degradation and the dehydrogenation products of Jervine, experiments were modelled after Rapson and Robinson (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1935, 1285). This type of Michael condensation was studied by various workers (Huber, *Ber.*, 1938, 71, 725; Bagchi and Banerjee, this *Journal*, 1946, 23, 397; Bhattacharyya, *ibid.*, 1956, 33, 545; Banerjee, Chatterjee, Sen Gupta and Bhattacharyya, *ibid.*, 1957, 34, 715; Dimroth, *Angew. Chem.*, 1947, 59, 215; Turner and Voile, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1950, 72, 4166; Johnson *et al.*, *ibid.*, 1950, 72, 3726; Brande and Wheeler, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1955, 329) for the synthesis of steroids. The condensation of 5-methoxy-1-indanone (I) with 1-acetyl- $\Delta^{1:2}$ -cyclohexene under the condition of Johnson *et al.* (*loc. cit.*) yielded a product as a yellow crystalline solid, which after chromatography furnished a ketone in white silky needles. This ketone may be represented by the structure (II) or (III).

The ultraviolet absorption spectra of the ketone λ_{max}^{air} 244 m μ (log ϵ 3.87), 292 m μ (log ϵ 4.04) and 323 m μ (log ϵ 4.35) indicate that this carbonyl function is in conjugation with the methoxystyrene system, as has been shown by Wilds *et al.* (*J.*

Amer. Chem. Soc., 1947, **69**, 1985; cf. Birch *et al.*, *J., Chem. Soc.*, 1957, 1339) with the compounds having the above type of chromophoric system. The absorption of only one mole of hydrogen per mole of this unsaturated ketone, on catalytic reduction, clearly points to the presence of only one reducible double bond. Further, the resulting dihydro compound showed only the characteristic absorption of anisole nucleus in the ultraviolet. From all these considerations the parent unsaturated ketone may be represented by the structure (II). This conclusion was proved by the degradative studies (Banerjee *et al.*, *loc. cit.*), schematically indicated below :

The reduced ketone (IV) on treatment with perbenzoic acid in chloroform solution furnished the desired lactone (V), but only in moderate yield by the best condition so far studied. This low yield of the lactone is in conformity with the observation that in the reaction with perbenzoic acid in chloroform solution, the solvent used in the earlier work (*J. Org. Chem.*, 1950, **15**, 1197) there is a tendency for aromatic rings to be attacked (Gutsche and Fleming, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1954, **76**, 1771; cf. Milas and Schofield, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1956, 4213). The lactone (V) was hydrolysed by alkali to the hydroxy-acid (VI) in 68% yield. The structure of the latter was established from its neutral equivalent data and its transformation with dilute sulphuric acid back to the original lactone. Similar easy lactonisation to form seven-membered lactones has been observed by Banerjee *et al.* (*loc. cit.*) and Rothman *et al.* (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1954, **76**, 527). The structure (VI) for the hydroxy-acid is preferred because of the fact that in the peracid oxidation of ketone to the lactone, the extra oxygen atom usually gets itself attached to the more substituted carbon atom (Doering and Speers, *ibid.*, 1950, **72**, 5515).

* E X P E R I M E N T A L

5-Keto-9-methoxy-1 : 2 : 3 : 4 : 4a : 5 : 11a : 11b-octahydrochrysofluorene (II).—To a solution of potassium metal (1.15 g.) in *tert.*-butanol (29 c.c.) cooled in ice-water, was added dropwise with constant shaking under nitrogen atmosphere a solution of 1-acetyl- $\Delta^{1:2}$ -cyclohexene (4 g.) [λ_{max} 232 m μ ($\log \epsilon$ 3.97)] and 5-methoxy-1-indanone (4.3 g.), prepared according to the procedure of Ingold and Piggott (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1923, 128, 1479) in dry thiophene-free benzene (50 c.c.). The reaction mixture, which was

*All melting points are uncorrected. The ultraviolet absorption spectrum was determined in ethanol (95%) by the Unicam spectrophotometer, S.P. 500.

greenish in colour during the addition, became dark red after some time and was allowed to stand for 48 hours at room temperature. It was refluxed for 4 hours and then acidified with cold dilute acetic acid. After working up in the usual way (Banerjee *et al.*, *loc. cit.*), the crude solid product was sublimed at $190-95^{\circ}/0.2$ mm to yield a slightly yellow-coloured material (2.5 g.), m.p. $150-52^{\circ}$. A solution of this coloured material (2.5 g.) in a mixture of 90% petroleum ether ($60-80^{\circ}$) and 10% benzene was absorbed on a column of activated alumina (Merck and Co., 75 g.) and the chromatogram was eluted with the above mixture of solvents. Twenty fractions (150 c.c. each) were collected. Each fraction, from the third to the twentieth, yielded a white crystalline solid, m.p. $152-53^{\circ}$. The total crystalline material (1.9 g.) was collected together, a part of which was recrystallised three times from methanol to furnish white silky needles, m.p. $155-56^{\circ}$; $\lambda_{\max}$ 244 $m\mu$ ($\log \epsilon$ 3.87), 292 $m\mu$ ($\log \epsilon$ 4.04) and 323 $m\mu$ ($\log \epsilon$ 4.35). (Found: C, 80.74; H, 7.43. $C_{18}H_{20}O_2$ requires C, 80.59; H, 7.46%).

The above crystalline unsaturated ketone (100 mg.), 2:4-dinitrophenylhydrazine (90 mg.), absolute ethanol (60 c.c.) and 2 drops of HCl (conc.) were heated to furnish red silky needles, m.p. $233-35^{\circ}$. It was purified by chromatography on alumina (6 g.) with benzene as the solvent to furnish a red silky material (110 mg.), m.p. $244-45^{\circ}$, which was crystallised three times from a mixture of benzene and ethyl acetate to afford red silky needles, m.p. $246-47^{\circ}$. (Found: N, 12.15. $C_{24}H_{24}O_4N_4$ requires N, 12.50%).

5-Keto-9-methoxy-1:2:3:4:4a:5:6:6a:11a:11b-decalhydrochrysofluorene (IV).

—The above unsaturated ketone (620 mg.) was catalytically hydrogenated in ethanol (120 c.c.) solution over 10% palladium on charcoal catalyst (0.2 g.). The calculated amount of hydrogen was absorbed within 4 hours. The stirring was continued until the absorption of hydrogen had ceased. The catalyst was removed by filtration, and the white crystalline material, m.p. 125° , obtained on removal of the solvent, was recrystallised three times from methanol to furnish the pure white crystalline reduced product (520 mg.), m.p. $140-41^{\circ}$, $\lambda_{\max}$ 279 $m\mu$ ($\log \epsilon$ 3.4). (Found: C, 80.43; H, 8.34. $C_{18}H_{22}O_2$ requires C, 80.00; H, 8.14%).

The yellow crystalline 2:4-dinitrophenylhydrazone (50 mg.), m.p. $192-95^{\circ}$, obtained from the saturated ketone (50 mg.) as above, was once crystallised from a mixture of benzene and ethyl acetate to yield crystals, m.p. 201° , which were again recrystallised twice from ethyl acetate to furnish yellow flakes, m.p. 204° . (Found: N, 12.65. $C_{24}H_{24}O_4N_4$ requires N, 12.44%).

Lactone of 5-Methoxy-2-(2'-hydroxycyclohexyl)-hydrindene 1-acetic Acid (V).—To the saturated ketone (200 mg.) in a test tube covered with black paper was added a solution of perbenzoic acid in chloroform (7 c.c., 3%). The reaction mixture was allowed to stand for 24 hours in the refrigerator. A blank experiment was also performed simultaneously. After titration which indicated the utilisation of one mole of perbenzoic acid, the reaction mixture was worked up as usual. The solid residue thus obtained was once crystallised from a mixture of benzene and petroleum ether ($60-80^{\circ}$) to afford white silky needles (90 mg.), m.p. $166-67^{\circ}$. This was crystallised thrice from the above mixture of solvents to furnish the pure lactone, m.p. 173° . (Found: C, 75.28; H, 7.88. $C_{18}H_{22}O_3$ requires C, 75.52; H, 7.69%).

Using the same quantities of the saturated ketone and the chloroform solution of perbenzoic acid as above, but allowing the reaction mixtures to stand for (i) 48 hours in the refrigerator and (ii) 48 hours in the refrigerator and 24 hours at the room temperature, yields of the desired lactone were 80 mg. and 40 mg. respectively.

5-Methoxy-2-(2'-hydroxycyclohexyl)-hydrindene-1-acetic Acid (VI).—To a solution of the lactone (170 mg.) in distilled methanol (2 c.c.) was added a methanolic KOH solution (4 c.c., 10%). The mixture was refluxed for 4 hours on the water-bath. Most of the methanol was removed and water (10 c.c.) was added, when a clear solution was obtained. This was extracted twice with ether. The aqueous solution was acidified with cold dilute sulphuric acid solution (2%), when a white crystalline solid was precipitated which was filtered. The crude hydroxy-acid (122 mg.), m.p. 136-37°, was recrystallised thrice from a mixture of ether and petroleum ether (60-80°), when beautiful white crystals of the hydroxy-acid, m.p. 145-46°, were obtained. (Found: C, 71.01; H, 7.86; N.E., 310. $C_{18}H_{24}O_4$ requires C, 71.05; H, 7.89%; N.E., 304).

The lactonisation of the above hydroxy-acid was carried out by heating the pure hydroxy-acid (10 mg.) with H_2SO_4 (20%) for 2 hours on a water-bath. The solid was filtered and dried to yield a crystalline material (6 mg.), m.p. 170°, which was once crystallised from a mixture of benzene and petroleum ether to furnish silky needles, m.p. 172-73°. The mixed melting point of this solid and the pure lactone, m.p. 173°, remained undepressed.

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